

Code for “Examining the Characteristics and Evolution of Wintertime Temperature Whiplash Events in the United States Southern Plains” (Giannakopoulos and Furtado 2025)

Scripts

tsi_calc.py - Calculation of the Southern Plains Temperature Swing Index

whiplash_definition.py – Defines temperature whiplash events for the study and creates figure 1

trends_fig_manuscript.py – Calculates and creates figure 2

height_composites.py – Calculates and creates figures 3 and 4

vT_Composites_HtoCWhiplashes.py - Calculates and creates figure 5

weather_regime_figure.py – Creates figure 6

Documents

daily_tsi_index_allmonths.nc – The daily Temperature Swing Index across the United States from 1950-2023 using ERA5

hc_whiplash_xarr_final.nc – Cot-to-cold whiplash database

ch_whiplash_xarr_final.nc – Cold-to-hot whiplash database

detrended_regimes_1950_2023_NDJFM.txt – Weather regimes from 1950-2023 (provided by Oliver Millin)

MK_refl_ind_1950_2022.txt – Daily Reflection Index from 1950-2022